
INNOVATIVE TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY CLASSES AS A MEANS OF IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LEARNING

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Annotation.

The article presents the experience of using innovative forms of teaching English in order to improve the effectiveness of teaching. Innovative forms of education contribute to the organization and activation of students' learning activities, increase the effectiveness of learning, create a favorable microclimate in English lessons.

Keywords.

innovation, critical thinking technology, technology, project technology, interactive teaching methods, technology elements, multidimensional didactic technology

Innovative forms of education are characterized by high communicative ability and active involvement of students in educational activities, activate the potential of knowledge and skills of speaking and listening skills, develop effectively the skills of communicative competence. This contributes to adaptation to modern social conditions, because society needs people who are quickly oriented in the modern world, independent and proactive, achieving success in their activities. Any innovative activity is based on creativity. Creative activity involves the development of the emotional and intellectual spheres of personality. This is one of the main tasks of the modern educational process. Educational activity requires the use of specific technologies that provide a solution to this problem. These are innovative forms of learning: role-playing, project method, ICT, techniques of critical thinking technology, multidimensional didactic technology.

The technology that stimulates the interests of students and develops the desire to learn is associated with the implementation of various kinds of projects. The use of this technology allows us to provide for all possible forms of work in a group: individual, group, collective, which stimulate the independence and creativity of student.

Techniques of critical thinking technology in English lessons teach students the organization of their activities, the ability to think, competent and meaningful reading, the ability to cooperate, etc.

During the lesson, it is possible to use both mini -projects designed for one lesson or part of it, and large projects that require a long time to complete them. Projects can be individual and group. The following project tasks were used in the 1st year:

1. the students are offered project topics: for example, an oral description of the appearance of their coursemates, their character, professions and their hobbies (for example, "I am about myself" (my name, the names of my parents, sisters, brothers; address; my age; birthday; my appearance; my interests).

2. Section 2. "Description of the area". The guys make a postcard-a description of their hometown (name; geographical location; monuments; my favorite places).

3. Section 3. "Cultural and national traditions, local history, customs and holidays of Great Britain".

At the lesson on the topic "Travel to London", a situation was proposed: students won a ticket to London, they want to learn more about the sights of the capital. Some of the guys will live in an English family. They fly to London by plane. The type of project is mixed, because it has signs of research, creative and role-playing projects. The work on the project was carried out in several stages. At the first lesson, the students were offered a situation and a discussion of the main content of the future project was organized. As a result of the discussion, problems

were selected, areas of work were highlighted, and a project plan was drawn up. Working materials were produced for the project: a mock-up of a map of London, photographs and 'slide presentations' of London's sights, a draft of the guide "Sights of London", layouts of shop windows and cafes, the necessary props were prepared. At the initial stage of the lesson, repetition and clichés of an etiquette nature are organized ("In the store", "In a cafe", "Asking for directions", etc.).

After fixing the speech material, each group presented its own message. The guys of group-No.1 staged the landing on the plane. The "stewardess" made a landing, greeting passengers, asked them to present a ticket, go to the cabin of the aircraft, served them during the flight. The guys who got the role of passengers asked to drink water, juice, tea, listen to music, ordered lunch. The guys of group No. 2, upon arrival at the hotel, were sent to an English family for further accommodation. This group conducted a story-role-playing game "Visiting the Smith family", using speech clichés of an etiquette nature, dialogue - questioning, monologue statements. The members of group No. 3 went to the store, and group No. 4 went to have dinner in a cafe. All participants in these stages of the lesson approached the task very responsibly, especially the "weak" students.

In the evening, most of the participants went to see the sights of London. Using speech clichés combined in the group "Asking the Way", they asked a local resident how to get to a given landmark. Listening to the explanations of a local resident, we drew our way on the map, followed the layout of the map of the center of London to the desired object. Confirmation of the correctness of the task was the appearance on the interactive whiteboard of a slide with the image of the desired attraction. All stages of the lesson were accompanied by a Power Point presentation prepared by the joint efforts of students and a teacher. The main objectives of such classes are practical, teacher-modeled tasks that activate listening and speaking skills. At the end of the lesson, the results were summed up:

What have the students learned linguistically? (They know how to buy something in a store, make an order in a cafe, ask for directions.)

How has their communication activity changed? (They can, interacting with each other, collectively politely thank, ask, offer, refuse, etc.)

What is the contribution of the project to the overall development of the student? (He can play a role, speak expressively and emotionally.)

What universal actions have the guys mastered? (They can independently search for the necessary information.)

I use the following techniques in the lessons: "Right and wrong statements", "Confused logical chains", "Key terms".

The author V.G.Timofeev "Up & up" for adults, there are enough similar tasks, so I try to use something new. For example: correlate the elements (the beginning and the end of the sentence) with each other and combine them into pairs. The techniques of this technology give the student the opportunity to express his point of view about the topic being studied freely, without fear of making mistakes and being corrected, to fix all statements: since any of them will be important for further work.

Interactive teaching methods are especially effective when studying the grammatical aspect of the English language. Let's take a closer look at several interactive learning technologies that are widely used by me in the classroom. For example, the technology of working in pairs or triples, both permanent and rotational (replaceable).

Group work is also not new and is well known to everyone. I often use rotating small groups in my lessons. For example, within the framework of the topic of the 1st course "Country studies. Great Britain", it is not the first year that I have been practicing work according to the following scheme:

Stage 1 – an advanced task, collecting information according to a certain plan about one of the four parts of the United Kingdom (it is ideal to work with a multiple of four students, I had 12). The choice of the part is made by drawing lots. Stage 2 – work in small groups in Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, England. The guys share the information found, systematize it.

Stage 3 – work in small groups United Kingdom. Each student brings information about his part to the entire team of the group.

Stage 4 – compare the completed tables, supplement the material, exchange opinions, prepare mini-stories about the United Kingdom.

In an effort to improve the process of learning foreign languages, I conduct classes using a PC. A variety of multimedia games contribute to the expansion of vocabulary, introduce the grammar of the English language, teach you to understand speech by ear, write correctly. Computer programs combine color graphics, videos, and music. I use such programs as "Euro Talk", "Learn to Speak English". Fragmentary use of these programs allows you to increase the motivation and interest of children in the subject. I use it when studying topics: "Numerals", "Shops and purchases", etc. These programs also provide knowledge control on each topic. The guys are happy to work at the computer. Projects with a

presentation in Power Point are carried out on almost every topic. I also use the technology of didactic multidimensional tools (DMI), the author of which is Valery Steinberg, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. The working tools of this technology are logical and semantic models. The guys really like to independently acquire knowledge on the topic of the lesson. The models are multifunctional because I use them at various stages of training: during initial acquaintance with new material, during its consolidation, during generalization and systematization of knowledge, their correction and control.

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